

Gender Based Discrimination in India through Ages

Amar Nath Upadhyay

Research Scholar, Department of Political Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

Perfect equality seems to be distant dream in the human society. A host of discriminations ie social, cultural, religious, sex, have been existent in all the societies throughout the ages. Indian society is no exception. No civilization in the world ever had perfect equality between the sexes. Discrimination based on the role and status has always existed in some form of the other in all the civilizations. The issue of male – female equality differed at different times in the history of India. In the ancient Vedic period the women enjoyed a very respectable position in the Indian society. They were free and treated equally with men. They were given same rights to education, marriage, wealth. They were free to educate themselves. They could participate freely in the debate with men. They would get married at an adult age and with their consent. The practice of widow remarriage was also prevalent. Post Vedic period, women lost their equal status for which they are still struggling. This period is dubbed as ‘dark Period’ for women. The women were treated merely as object and their role was only that of a servant to man. Their right to Upanayana and education were withdrawn. They were confined to the house and could not go openly to the public places. The women were destined to serve their husbands. A widow girl child was not allowed to remarry. Leading to a miserable life. During the Medieval time, when the Arabs started invading India Women’s Status got corroded. Women were restricted to protect themselves from the religious culture of Islam. Religious and caste differences grew stronger. Veil system was introduced. The women were imprisoned in the four walls of the house. The practice of child marriage continued. The widows were forced to follow the ritual of ‘Sati’. The women were even sold as slaves. The women suffered from many kinds of injustice and hardships. During the British period, many Indian leaders pitched for the complete abolition of the ill practices subordinating the women. The British nacted laws to eliminate the practices responsible for the miserable condition of the women. However British rule bore the disadvantages too. The British economically exploited India and disrupted her rural handicraft industries. Late Dada Bhai Navroji, in his celebrated book “Poverty and the Unbritish Rule in India” has shed light on the British exploitation of India. It does not mean that British rule in India was not in the interest of indians. There are certain implications. They unified India into one nation state and gave us the federal political system; they also created a proper nationwide administrative system. They introduced modern educational system along with postal system. The advent of British gave a blow to the traditional customs in India. The Christian missionaries started criticizing the ill treatment and barbaric practice of ‘Sati’. Some Indian social thinkers like Raja Ram Mohan Roy got attracted to this view. He raised his voice against the inhuman practice of ‘Sati’. The British administration took positive steps to curb the evil social customs practiced in India. Sati Restriction Act was passed in 1829 and Hindu-widow Remarriage Act was enacted in 1865. The provincial government was empowered to pass independent acts to reduce the age of marriage for the girls. The British Government took few good steps to improve the condition of Indian Women. But social and cultural customs are hard to break. The practice of ‘Sati’ was discontinued but early marriages of young girls are still continued.

India achieved Independence in 1947. Since then the Indian society has gone through developments in various spheres. The government decided to go for five year planning method to materialize socio-economic development. In spite of a large increase in the population there are positive developments in the per capita incomes, living standards, educational attainments,

industrialization, transport and communications. But we cannot say that there is the desired equality between man and women. The women are still discriminated against in many socioeconomic and other spheres. United Nations Development Fund for Women (UNIFEM) Report Kofi Annan, Secretary General of the United Nations, declared in the 2006 report posted on the United Nations Development Fund for Women (UNIFEM) website that, "Violence against women is a problem of pandemic proportions. At least one out of every three women around the world has been coerced into sex and beaten or otherwise abused in her lifetime especially by the abuser someone usually known to her". Violence against women can be categorized into several broad categories. These include violence carried out by individuals as well as states. Some of the forms of violence by individuals are sexual harassment, rape, coercive use of contraceptives, domestic violence, prenatal sex selection, female infanticide, harmful customary practices like dowry violence, honor killings, marriage by abduction, female genital mutilation, and forced marriage.

Female foeticide is one of the worst forms of violence practiced against women where she is denied her most basic, natural and fundamental right, that is right to life which enshrined in article 21 of the Indian Constitution. Prenatal sex determination followed by female foetus abortion denied the girl child the very opportunity of being born. The preference for male child over a female child is universal but it has been an obsession in Indian Society. Giving birth to a male child is considered as the ultimate aim of a woman. A woman bearing a male child is treated with respect, whereas a woman bearing female child is despised and neglected. The birth of a male child is celebrated with pomp, whereas the birth of female child rarely celebrated. The son is always considered as the caretaker and security for the old age by the parents. A daughter on the other hand, is thought to be a big liability. Investment on her upbringing and education is considered to be wasteful financial liability. Later a large sum of money has to be spent on her marriage in addition to huge amount of dowry. The very insecure nature of female life is also an important cause of dislike for a female child. The life of female child remains insecure right from the birth till her death. The girl has to be always protected from the prying eyes of the anti-social elements. They are often molested, abducted and raped by not only strangers but by their own relatives. The parents of the girl child have to be always careful. When the girl is in school and then college the parents fear that she may get corrupting influence of the society. She is constantly watched and all her moves are monitored curbing their freedom. Dropout rates of the girls are higher therefore, parents both in urban as well as rural areas go in for sex determination of the fetus and later aborted of the female foetus. Married girls do not claim their legal share in the landed property and if they do so, she would most likely, lose their affection of her parents and brothers. As an adult person women do not enjoy equal status with men. In the house usually the husband takes all the decisions and the wife hardly has any voice. If the wife happens to be working women, then she has to perform double the work. Housekeeping is considered to be her primary works even if she works full time at her job. If the woman is merely house maker then her domestic chores are not acknowledged. Performing household chores daily and taking care of children and aged persons by the women are taken for granted. This has been due to the influence of the culture. Household work gets no recognition as an economic activity. In most of the homes the women eat food after the other members finish their meals. Often little or no food is left for her poor diet causes malnutrition among the woman. Therefore, most women have poor hemoglobin count and often keep on suffering from minor diseases. As compared to males the women are not given prompt medical facilities. This also has adverse effect on their health. Discrimination treatment right from the birth or rather from before birth has an above psychological effect on

the women. They lose their own self-esteem and confidence. He is shy to take up challenges and accept secondary roles to their male counterparts about by various agencies.

Global level efforts were put forth to eliminate gender based discrimination. The 1993 UN Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women was the first international instrument which explicitly defined and addressed the issue of gender discrimination and violence against women. This declaration specifically refers to the present nature of gender inequalities in understanding violence against women. It also discussed various facets of gender discrimination and the atrocities perpetrated on the women the world over. This UN Declaration and the discussion of the world conference on Human Rights held in the same year (1993), is often viewed as the “turning point” for the issue of gender discrimination. After 1993 the international community began to serious think about gender discrimination violence against women as a very serious issue.

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